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Revisiting Slag Eye in Molten Steel

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ABSTRACT

Slag eye formation due to gas bubbling in metallurgical processes like steelmaking is a frequently encountered phenomenon, which can significantly hamper the efficiency of steel production process. Control over occurrence of slag eye thus becomes essential to obtain better product quality. The present study aims to revisit past investigations into slag eye formation. It looks at various models developed to quantify this phenomenon and the justifications behind their formulation in order to establish the important parameters involved in slag eye formation. It then proceeds to review the more recently developed models in detail by testing their applicability against a range of data obtained from different experiments and plant measurements. The effect of viscosity is explored and models with and without viscous considerations are compared in specific context of steelmaking ladles.

It is observed that the models developed for well-developed eye sizes may not be well suited for scenarios involving smaller or critical eye sizes. Models are also restricted by the systems as well as slag thickness range to which they are applicable. Viscosity is observed to have minor effect on eye-size prediction. A modified form of an available expression is suggested for better prediction of eye-area for available plant data.

INTRODUCTION AND PAST INVESTIGATIONS

Gas bubbling is an important part of multiple metallurgical processes, one major application being in steelmaking. It is the primary method for recirculation of metal bath. In addition to temperature homogenization of the bath, it also enables removal of inclusions from the metal as well as homogenization of composition, allowing a controlled and uniform quality of final product. During continuous casting process, argon bubbling allows to prevent clogging of the SEN (Submerged Entry Nozzle).

Gas bubbling, however, also presents steelmakers with ramifications such as slag entrainment and formation of slag eye. As the gas is injected from the bottom of vessel, it forms an opening in the slag layer above the injection point (Figure 1). This opening exposes liquid metal to atmosphere, creating site for oxidation and severely degrading the quality of liquid metal. Slag-eye area depends on the slag layer thickness as well as the flow rate of the gas¹. Control over slag-eye formation can hence improve the quality as well as cycle time of the process. Several studies have been made on plant data as well as physical models to predict the slag-eye area as a function of process parameters viz., gas flow rate, slag thickness, bath dimensions and physical properties of gas and liquid. Various expressions have been suggested but they are limited by the systems addressed, the size range of slag-eye suggested, slag layer thickness etc.

Various past investigations pertaining to slag eye^{2,3,5,8,11,13} were explored and are further discussed in detail below.

Figure 1: Slag eye in a ladle

Yonezawa and Schwertfeger² were among the first to quantitatively study slag eye size, using measurements from industrial steelmaking ladle as well as experiments performed with a scaled mercury- silicon oil model, establishing a dependence of eye area, A_e on a Froude number based on gravitational acceleration g , flow rate Q , bath height H , slag height h :

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = f\left(\frac{Q^2}{gH^5}\right) \quad (1)$$

Their experimental data has since then been used by numerous investigators for validation of their own correlations. Subagyo *et al.*³ attempted to explain data corresponding to Eq. (1) in a unifying but less accurate manner. These initial investigations successfully established Froude number as an important factor in eye size determination. Mazumdar⁴ suggested a different Froude number, based on direct variables such as plume rise velocity (U_p) and bath height (H), as a representation of the kinetic and potential energies, respectively, in the bulk of fluid. The ladle Froude number was defined as:

$$Fr = \frac{U_p^2}{gH} \quad (2)$$

Mazumdar and Evans⁵ used Yonezawa's experimental and industrial data² with the consideration of ladle hydrodynamics to suggest the correlation:

$$\frac{A_e}{H^2} = k_1 \left(1 + \frac{h}{H}\right)^2 \left(1 - 2Fr \cdot \frac{h}{H}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The constants k_1 and k_2 are dependent on the system. Their work indicated that the dimensionless plume exposed area, $\frac{A_e}{H^2}$ can be correlated with two independent dimension – less variables namely, the dimensionless slag depth, $\frac{h}{H}$ and ladle Froude number defined by Eq. (2).

Iguchi *et al.*⁶ and Krishnapisharody and Irons⁷ prescribed correlations for slag eye as a function of bath and slag dimensions as well as the densities of melt and slag. These works explicitly established a significant role of physical properties of the system, which was not explored in previous models^{2-3,5}. In their more recent investigation⁸, the Krishnapisharody and Irons prescribed a correlation of eye size based on momentum balance in the peripheral region of the eye. The subsequent functional correlation suggested was of the form

$$\frac{A_e}{A_p} = \alpha + \beta \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gH} \right)^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

where

A_p is the area of plume at the slag –

metal interface, ρ_l is the density of melt and $\Delta\rho$ is the difference in densities of melt and slag. Using Eqs. (5) and (6) developed

from cold model experiments using water – motor oil, water – paraffin oil and CaCl₂ – paraffin oil systems^{9 – 10},

Krishnapisharody and Irons proposed Eq. (7) to predict eye size in terms of slag thickness, h , bath height H ,

and relative density of phases, ρ^* , non – dimensional flow rate, $Q^* \left(= \frac{Q}{\sqrt{gH^5}} \right)$ as

$$\frac{U_p}{\sqrt{gH}} = 1.16 \left(\frac{Q}{\sqrt{gH^5}} \right)^{0.32} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{A_p}{H^2} = 1.41 \left(\frac{Q}{\sqrt{gH^5}} \right)^{0.4} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{A_e}{A_p} = a + b(1 - \rho^*)^{-0.5} (Q^*)^{0.33} h^{*-0.5} \quad (7)$$

Where $h^* = \frac{h}{H}$. a and b in Eq. (7) are related to α and β in Eq. (4) approximately as $a = 1.41 \alpha$ and $b = 1.54 \beta$.

In 2011, Wu *et al.*¹¹ recorded cold model as well as industrial ladle data ranging from well-developed eye sizes for water model and industrial ladle to relatively smaller eye openings for a Galinstan – 12% HCl system. Consequently, the authors proposed semi-empirical correlations factoring in the values of parameters corresponding to critical condition for slag eye opening. The coefficients prescribed were dependent on the liquid system. Eq. (8) is defined for a water-silicon oil system, while Eq. (9) is prescribed for Galinstan(Ga-In-Sn) - 12% HCl.

$$A_e = 0.43 U_p^{3.645} H^{1.350} h^{-1.093} \quad (8)$$

$$A_e = 2.802 \left(U_p - 0.5 \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta\rho g h}{\rho_l}} \right)^{1.690} H^{1.220} h^{-0.015} \quad (9)$$

Plume rise velocity, U_p is defined by the expression suggested by Castello-Branco and Schwertfeger¹² as

$$U_p = 17.44 Q^{0.244} H^{-0.08} \rho_l^{0.0218} \quad (10)$$

The works listed above^{2,3,5,8,11} neglected the effects of viscous forces under the assumption of a Froude dominated flow, *i.e.*, dominance of inertia and gravity forces. Peranandhanathan and Mazumdar¹³ took into account the factor of slag viscosity, ν_s in their experimental modeling and, using Rayleigh's method of indices, suggested a relation of the form:

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = a \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gh} \right)^b \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^c \left(\frac{\nu_s}{hU_p} \right)^d \quad (11)$$

where

U_p is defined by Eq. (10). Reynolds number takes into account the viscous effect of the slag with the consideration that melt

has a much higher fluidity than slag. Consistent with the notion that that distant geometrical parameters like bath height

and radius should not have an effect in the vicinity of eye⁷, eye area was non – dimensionalised as $\frac{A_e}{h^2}$

but was subsequently replaced by $\frac{A_e}{hH}$ when the authors¹³ recognized a linear trend in $\frac{A_e}{h^2}$ with $\frac{h}{H}$, *i.e.*, relative slag thickness. The authors proposed the following correlation based on regression analysis:

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = 3.25 \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gh} \right)^{1.28} \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^{0.55} \left(\frac{v_s}{hU_p} \right)^{-0.05} \quad (12)$$

The expression performed well on data from previous experiments^{2,10-11} and is inclusive of all major parameters previously known to affect slag eye size, *viz.* the geometry, slag thickness and physical properties of the two phases.

MODELING PROCEDURE

Various investigators predicted the eye area for different systems based on gas flow rate, bath dimensions, slag thickness, different expressions for plume velocity and physical properties of system except surface tension, the role of which has not been identified and needs further attention, especially pertaining to critical eye formation, where length-scale for forces to act becomes small.

The aim of present study is to evaluate the expression better suited at predicting slag eye in steelmaking ladles. It is hence reasonable to test the expression against steel plant data in addition to experimental models. The dataset used for evaluation is listed in Table I and Table II. In order to determine adequacy of a model, the solver plugin of Microsoft Excel is setup to determine various coefficients of a suggested expression such that the coefficient of determination, R^2 approaches unity.

Table I: List of data used

Source	Abbreviation	System Description	System specifications			
			Bath height (m)	Diameter (m)	Flow rate ($10^{-5} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$)	Slag height (10^{-3} m)
Peranandhanthan and Mazumdar ¹³	P&M	Multiple water models-air	0.1377, 0.162, 0.255, 0.3	0.15	1.67, 3.33, 5.0, 6.67	2.5-9.0
Yonezawa and Schwertfeger ²	Y&S: Hg Sil Oil	Mercury-Silicon Oil-Nitrogen	0.225	0.29	2.78-19.4	3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 15, 20, 30
Yonezawa and Schwertfeger ²	Y&S: Ladle	Steel-Slag-Argon	3.5	NA	583, 750, 1000, 1040, 1250	50
Sand <i>et al.</i> ¹⁴	S: Ladle	CFD based simulation	2.8	NA	333	100
Han <i>et al.</i> ¹⁵	H: Water Sil Oil	Water-Silicon Oil-air	0.3846	0.16	0.5, 0.83, 1.17, 1.67	2.5, 8, 10
Wu <i>et al.</i> ¹¹	W: Water Sil Oil	Water-Silicon Oil-air	0.35, 0.4, 0.45	0.6	1.5, 2.5, 3.5, 7.5	15, 20, 25
Wu <i>et al.</i> ¹¹	W: Ladle	Steel-Slag-Argon	3.81	NA	400-1100	25, 40, 50, 60
Wu <i>et al.</i> ¹¹	W: Galinstan HCl	GaInSn-12%HCl-Argon	0.1, 0.145	0.24	3.5-14.0	15, 20, 30

Table II: Physical properties of constituents of systems in Table I

Fluid	Viscosity (Pa-s)	Density (kg/m ³)
Water ¹³	0.0009125	1000
Petroleum ether ¹³	0.00038	640
Mustard oil ¹³	0.07	895
Soyabean oil ¹³	0.0693	910
C ₂ Cl ₄ ¹³	0.0008445	1622
Silicon oil variety 1 ²	0.05	960
Silicon oil variety 2 ²	0.1	960
Perfumed coconut oil ¹³	0.020999973	843
Mercury ²	0.0015504	13600
Steel (1873K) ²	0.006	7000
Slag ²	0.2664	3500
Ga-Sn-In alloy ¹¹	0.006	6400
HCl(12%) ¹¹	0.001	1060

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of Peranadhanathan and Mazumdar's correlation

Peranadhanathan and Mazumdar¹³, tested their water model based correlation against various data from the experimental and industrial measurements of Yonezawa and Shwertfeger² as well as experiments performed by Krishnapisharody and Irons⁷ and Wu *et al*¹¹. A comprehensive plot of fit for Eq. (12) is presented in Figure 2 while Figure 3 shows the dimensional form of eye area. The authors prescribed Eq. (12) to be valid for a slag thickness range of $0.006 \leq \frac{h}{H} \leq$

0.05, *i. e.*, under the thin slag approximation. Figure 4 shows the error in predictions of Eq. (12) as the slag thickness changes. It can be observed that for $\frac{h}{H} < 0.5$, the expression holds adequately, while data corresponding to thicker slags shows substantial error.

Figure 2: (a) Parity plot of Eq. (12) for data listed in Table I. (b) Magnified plot of highlighted region in (a)

Figure 3: Plot of area in dimensional form

Figure 4: Error generated by Eq. (12) with changing slag thickness

As is evident in Figure 3, Eq. (12) which is developed based on water-oil systems, while showing good results for experimental setups like water-silicon oil, Hg-silicon oil etc., does not agree well with data from steelmaking ladles, as observed by the under-prediction of eye size for ladles. It can be observed in Figure 4 and Figure 5 that the cases involving thicker slag, subsequently resulted in smaller eye sizes, as would be expected if other conditions remain similar. The work done by Wu *et al.*¹¹ with Galinstan alloy shows recorded eye sizes which are smaller than those observed in other experiments. Similar erroneous predictions are also observed for smaller eye sizes in Hg- Silicon oil model². It can hence be concluded that Eq. (12) is well suited for thin slag and well- developed slag eye but does not predict well small eye sizes close to critical eye formation.

Figure 5: Error generated by Eq. (12) with changing eye area

Assessment of viscous effect in Peranadhanathan and Mazumdar's correlation

Eq. (12) presents a novel addition to factors involved in slag eye formation by adding viscous effects through Reynolds number using slag layer viscosity, which is justified since the melt is much less viscous. Krishnapisharody and Irons⁷ showed that in a given ladle system, central as well as eccentric nozzle show similar trends in eye size. In a system sufficiently large to not have the bath circumference influence slag eye vicinity, the assumption of a free-moving slag layer is reasonable. In absence of a fixed boundary layer, Reynolds number loses significance¹⁶. The following functional relationship is used to evaluate the same, replacing Reynolds number with relative viscosity of the two phases, $\frac{\nu_s}{\nu_l}$, thus incorporating viscous effects of melt, if any:

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = a \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gh} \right)^b \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^c \left(\frac{\nu_s}{\nu_l} \right)^d \quad (13)$$

Similar to the formulation of Eq. (12), numerical coefficients are generated to provide best fit to data from Peranadhanathan and Mazumdar's work¹³. The resultant numerical equation is

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = 5.12 \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gh} \right)^{1.24} \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^{0.53} \left(\frac{\nu_s}{\nu_l} \right)^{-0.06} \quad (14)$$

The coefficients of Eq. (14) are similar to those of Eq. (12), indicating that the relative viscosity of the system can be used alternatively to Reynolds number while maintaining reasonable accuracy in prediction. However, the very small changes to the overall expression upon changing viscous effects also points to the buoyancy driven nature of the flow, concurrent to past investigations^{2,3,5,8,11}. As discussed in the formulation of Eq. (14) a reasonably large vessel tends to have small effect of boundaries on the phenomenon happening at core of the bulk. The Reynolds number assumption considering a free-flowing slag-metal interface can also be extended as an argument for free stream flow in the bulk and hence, an absence of any major viscous forces. Keeping this in view, Eq. (15) tries to assess the effect of viscous factor.

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = a \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gh} \right)^b \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^c \quad (15)$$

Similar to previous cases, the numerical values of coefficients generated through regression result in the expression:

$$\frac{A_e}{hH} = 5.92 \left(\frac{U_p^2}{gh} \right)^{1.25} \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\Delta\rho} \right)^{0.35} \quad (16)$$

In order to further outline the viscous effects, Table III compares the performance of Eqs. (12), (14) and (16) against the different data. It can be observed that Eq. (16) fairs reasonably well in predicting data from steelmaking ladles. The effect of viscosity can thus safely be assumed to be small, if not negligible in slag eye formation. Krishnapisharody and Irons¹⁰ considered metal-slag interactions purely dominated by gravity and inertial forces with no effect of viscosity.

Table III: Comparison of accuracy of Eq. (12) and derived Eqs. (14), (16)

Data	Eq. (12)	Eq. (14)	Eq. (16)
P&M	±40%	±40%	±40%
Y&S: Hg Sil Oil	-100%	-100%	-20% to -100%
Y&S: Ladle	Upto 30%	Upto 45%	Upto 25%
H: Water Sil Oil	≤10%	-50% to +20%	±40%
W: Water Sil Oil	Upto 80%	Upto 80%	Over 100%
W: Ladle	Upto 50%	Upto 80%	Upto 50%
W: GaInSn HCl	-100%	-100%	-100%
S: Ladle ($A_p = 0.4 \text{ m}^2$)	0.68 m^2	0.56 m^2	0.71 m^2

Evaluation of Krishnapisharody and Irons' correlation

Eq. (5) presents the functional relationship governing Krishnapisharody and Irons' formulation⁸. The authors performed a set of cold model experiments using Water-motor oil, Water-paraffin oil and CaCl_2 -paraffin oil systems. Based on the obtained results collectively with industrial and experimental data from the works of Yonezawa and Schwertfeger² and Han *et al.*,¹⁵ Krishnapisharody and Irons determined numerical values of coefficients to Eq.(7) and further substituting Eqs. (5) and (6), proposed the correlation:

$$\frac{A_e}{H^2} = -0.76Q^{*0.4} + 7.15(1 - \rho^*)^{-0.5}(Q^*)^{0.73} h^{*-0.5} \quad (17)$$

Parity plot for Eq. (17) in Figure 6 shows that while the ratio $\frac{A_e}{A_p}$ in the authors' original formulation showed converging data⁸, the actual values of eye area show high error for the given correlation. In particular it does not predict well eye sizes in ladle metallurgy applications, as can be seen in Figure 6, where the predicted and measured area differ by an order of magnitude resulting in a non-random error in predicted values.

Figure 6: (a) Parity plot for Eq. (17) and (b) Error in prediction with changing Froude number

Since the functional relationship suggested by Eq. (17) has directly measurable quantities, as opposed to the plume area, A_p , employed in Eq. (7). With the aim to generate coefficients suited to predict steelmaking ladle scenario with efficiency, keeping the functional equation same as for Eq. (17) and running regression analysis on Yonezawa and Schwertfeger's data² results in the correlation:

$$\frac{A_e}{H^2} = -0.108Q^{*0.4} + 1.2(1 - \rho^*)^{-0.5}(Q^*)^{0.73} h^{*-0.5} \quad (18)$$

Parity plot for Eq. (18) has been shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that the expression also adequately explains values from the other two industrial datasets by Wu *et al.*¹¹ and Sand *et al.*¹⁴

Figure 7: (a) Parity plot for Eq. (18) and (b) Error in prediction

A comparison with Figure 3 showing the prediction for Eq. (12), indicates that Eq. (5) and subsequently generated numerical correlation in Eq. (18), although with a loss of generality in terms of including various effects involved, are able to accurately predict eye sizes from multiple industrial sources^{2,11,14}.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The dimension of slag eye is primarily governed by Froude dominated fluid flow, *i.e.*, majorly under the influence of gravitational and inertial forces. It has been verified that neglecting the effect of viscosity does not affect the accuracy of predictions owing to the contribution of viscous forces being very small. The models developed under such buoyancy driven consideration have been developed for well-developed eye sizes. While they are suitable for predictions involving steelmaking ladles, they prove ineffective in predictions pertaining to critical parameters like flow rate, dimensions etc. required to avoid eye formation, as maybe required for processes like continuous casting, where factors like viscosity of slag and surface tension based adhesive interactions at slag-metal interface can become important. These need to be further explored and can possibly be related to and derived from studies on slag entrainment, where shear forces play an important role.

The following expression, which has been developed and verified against three independent industrial datasets, may be employed to predict slag eye size in ladle metallurgy applications:

$$\frac{A_e}{H^2} = -0.108Q^{*0.4} + 1.2(1 - \rho^*)^{-0.5}(Q^*)^{0.73} h^{*-0.5}$$

It has been developed under thin slag approximation and although it cannot be generalized for multiple two phase systems, it is well suited to predict and subsequently have a degree of control over slag eye size in steelmaking ladles.

REFERENCES

1. Y. Liu, Z. He, and L. Pan, "Numerical Investigations on the Slag Eye in Steel Ladles", *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 2014, Article ID 834103.
2. K. Yonezawa and K. Shwertfeger, "Spout Eyes Formed by an Emerging Gas Plume at the Surface of a Slag-Covered Metal Melt", *Metall. Mater. Trans.*, 30B (1999), pp. 411-418.
3. S. Subagyo, G. A. Brooks and G. A. Irons, "Spout Eyes Area Correlation in Ladle Metallurgy", *ISIJ Int.*, 43, No. 2 (2003), pp. 262.
4. D. Mazumdar, "Dynamic Similarity Considerations in Gas-Stirred Ladle Systems", *Metall. Trans.*, 21B (1990), pp. 925-928.
5. D. Mazumdar and J. W. Evans, "A Model for Estimating Exposed Plume Eye Area in Steel Refining Ladles Covered with Thin Slag", *Metall. Trans.*, 35B (2004), pp. 400-404.
6. M. Iguchi, K. Miyamoto, S. Yamashita, D. Iguchi and M. Zeze, "Spout Eye Area in Ladle Refining Process", *ISIJ Int.*, 44, No. 3 (2004), pp. 636-638.
7. K. Krishnapisharody and G. A. Irons, "Modeling of Slag Eye Formation over a Metal Bath Due to Gas Bubbling," *Metall. Mater. Trans.*, 37B (2006), pp. 763-72.
8. K. Krishnapisharody and G. A. Irons, "An Extended Model for Slag Eye Size in Ladle Metallurgy", *ISIJ Int.*, 48, No. 12 (2007), pp. 1807-1809.
9. K. Krishnapisharody and G. A. Irons, "A Study of Spouts on Bath Surfaces from Gas Bubbling, Part I: Experimental Investigation", *Metall. Trans.*, 38B (2007), pp. 367-375.
10. K. Krishnapisharody and G. A. Irons, "A Study of Spouts on Bath Surfaces from Gas Bubbling, Part II: Elucidation of Plume Dynamics", *Metall. Trans.*, 38B (2007), pp. 377-388.
11. L. Wu, P. Valentin, and D. Sichen, "Study of Open Eye Formation in an Argon Stirred Ladle", *Steel Res. Int.*, vol. 81 (2010), pp. 508-15.
12. M. A. S. C. Castello-Branco and K. Shwertfeger, "Large-Scale Measurements of the Physical Characteristics of Round Vertical Bubble Plumes in Liquids", *Metall. Trans.*, 25B(1994), pp. 359-371.
13. M. Peranandhanathan and D. Mazumdar, "Modeling of Slag Eye Area in Argon Stirred Ladles", *ISIJ Int.*, Vol. 50, No. 11 (2010), pp. 1622-1631.
14. U. Sand, H. Yang, J. Eriksson and R. B. Fdhila, "Control of Gas Bubbles and Slag Layer in Ladle Furnace by Electromagnetic Stirring", *Iron and Steel Technology, AISTech* (July 2009).
15. J. Han, S. Heo, D. Kam, B. You, J. Pak and H. Song, "Transient Fluid Flow Phenomena in a Gas Stirred Liquid Bath with Top Oil Layer—Approach by Numerical Simulation and Water Model Experiments", *ISIJ Int.*, 41, No. 10 (2001), pp. 1165-1173.
16. A. Bejan, "Laminar Boundary Layer Flow", *Convection Heat Transfer*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey (2013), pp. 37-42.